

Dielectrophoretic Separation of Lipid-Protein Complex from Reconstituted Milk Whey

VIRENDRA P TYAGI^a and GYAN P. SHARMA^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, M. M. H. (P. G.) College, Ghaziabad-201 001

^bFood Research and Standardisation Laboratory, Ghaziabad-201 001

Manuscript received 23 November 1994, revised 19 May 1995 accepted 6 July 1995

Two types of electrode assembly, one slotted and the other needle-plate, are designed for dielectrophoretic separation of lipid-protein complex from a reconstituted milk whey. Effects of various factors, viz. frequency of electric fields, applied voltage, and pH etc. on the yield of separation have been studied. Maximum separation is achieved in the field frequency range of 45–55 kHz and at pH 2.3 and 6.3. The dielectrophoretic separation yield of lipid-proteins complex is maximum with 2.3 mm slot width of the dielectric barrier between the electrodes of slotted cell. The maxima of dielectrophoretic yield were obtained at lower threshold field frequency, in slotted electrode system as compared to needle-plate type electrode.

Electrophoresis and its derivative techniques particularly electro dialysis and membrane separation methods have found wide applications in biotechnology for separating liquid dispersions. But these methods have many limitations. The possibility of filtration process in non-uniform electric field was studied in detail^{1,2}. Dielectrophoretic separation of non-conducting liquids with stationary electrodes has been achieved by various workers³. Differential separation of some metal oxides has been carried out using moving electrode system⁴. It has been shown that dielectrophoresis can be used for differential separation of complex biological suspensions⁵ and the same has been successfully achieved⁶. Dielectrophoretic separation method is endowed with many advantages, e.g. the direction of force acting on dispersed particles does not depend upon the field direction and it prevents electrolysis and also the accompanying undesirable electrochemical reactions.

Results and Discussion

In needle-plate type electrode system non-uniformity

Fig. 1 Effect of frequency on dielectrophoretic yield in needle-plate electrode cell, pH 6.3; voltage applied for: (1) 20, (2) 30 (3) 40 and (4) 50 V

Fig. 2 Effect of voltage on dielectrophoretic yield in needle-plate electrode cell, pH 6.3; frequency for: (1) 100, (2) 150 and (3) 200 kHz.

of electric field is produced near the electrode. The motion of dispersed particles is directed from the needle to the plate electrode, i.e. towards the decreasing electric field strength as the polarisability of dispersion medium is higher than that of dispersed phase². The results (Fig. 1) show that dielectrophoretic yield of lipid-protein complex does not depend upon the field frequency in the range of 25–95 kHz. For the frequency less than 5 kHz the dielectrophoresis is accompanied by electrolysis of water. This adds an appreciable distortion of the transport of lipid and protein

Fig. 3. Effect of voltage on the dielectrophoretic yield in slotted DEP cell, pH 6.3; frequency for : (1) 20, (2) 40 and (3) 50 kHz.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the dielectrophoretic yield in needle-plate electrode cell, frequency 50 kHz; voltage applied for : (1) 50, (2) 40, (3) 30 and (4) 20 V.

particulates due to the escape of gas in the pre-electrode region, mainly near the needle. The transfer of lipid protein particulates fraction of milk whey is markedly intensified in the direction of motion of gas bubble. A negligible gas escape is observed for frequencies 5–20 kHz. An

intensive gas escape at needle is observed for all range of frequencies studied at the moment of abrupt circuit commutation. The undesirable process has been eliminated by the method of circuit commutation for zero voltage and then raising it smoothly upto a given value. It is also observed (Fig. 1) that as the intensity of electric field is increased by increasing the applied voltage, the lower frequency limit from where dielectrophoretic yield becomes independent of frequency change, also shifts towards the higher frequency. This critical frequency is 25 kHz for 20 V applied voltage and after gradual increase it shifts to 40 kHz for applied voltage of 50 V. For the frequency of 100 kHz the relation of yield with field intensity, i.e. applied voltage, shows parabolic character (Fig. 2) under similar conditions, the character of this curve appreciably changes at 125 kHz. It has also been observed that below 80 kHz, lipid-protein particle shows rotation near plate electrode.

In experiments with slotted electrode cells, higher intensity field region exists in slots or pores of dielectric barrier. Now suspended lipid-protein particles move towards planoparallel electrodes. It was observed that during the dielectrophoretic capture of lipid-protein particles at both electrodes, electrolysis is completely absent even for the lower frequencies range (upto 100 Hz). In slotted electrode system at comparatively low voltages, higher yield is also obtained (Fig. 3) while in needle-plate type of electrode system comparatively higher frequency and higher voltage give linear relation with dielectrophoretic yield of lipid-protein complex (Fig. 2).

Experiments have also been conducted to study the rate of dielectrophoretic yield with change in active acidity of medium for a given values of other parameters in needle-

Fig. 5. Effect of slot-width of dielectric barrier on the dielectrophoretic yield in slotted DEP cell, frequency 50 kHz, pH 6.3; voltage applied for : (1) 50, (2) 40 and (3) 30 V.

plate type electrode cell. It is indicated that dielectrophoretic yield is lowest at pH 4.9–5.3 (Fig. 4). This pH range also corresponds to minimum surface charge of protein. Dielectrophoretic yield increases with variation of pH from this specific $pH_{(ISO)}$ in both sides, i.e. increasing and decreasing pH.

In dielectric barrier electrode system the maximum yield is obtained with slot-width of 2.3 mm (Fig. 5). In other conditions of slot-width the yield is found appreciably low. This indicates that there is an optimum strength of non-uniform electric field for which dielectrophoretic force on lipid-protein particles is highest. In this electrode system the dielectrophoretic yield of lipid-protein complex is independent of any frequency change below frequency of 20 and above 80 kHz (Fig. 6). However, a clear maxima of yield is produced for 50 kHz. A comparative analysis of Figs. 1 and 6 shows that in slotted cell the threshold frequency values i.e. frequency (f_{max}) corresponding to yield extremum points, are appreciably lower than those of same parameter during dielectrophoresis in needle type electrode system. It is also clear that field frequency and the corresponding maximum yield of lipid-protein complex appreciably depend on the type of electrode system.

The presence of extremum in the frequency relationship of the dielectrophoretic yield and possibility of its shift along the frequency scale may find practical application in developing the separation process of biological dispersions on the basis of dielectrophoretic filtration. However, the necessity of explaining the mechanism of extremum formation in various parameters demands further investigation.

The results allow to recommend the use of dielectrophoresis in combination with membrane separation meth-

Fig. 6. Effect of frequency on the dielectrophoretic yield in slotted DEP cell, pH 6.3; voltage applied for: (1) 20, (2) 30, (3) 40 and (4) 50 V.

ods for preventing the sealing of membrane. Design of pores/slots in membrane may be achieved by considering the factors studied in slotted dielectrophoretic cell in order to obtain greater efficiency of filtration process. Application of the varying field with sharp, non-homogeneity in the membrane region of the filtering dispersion, provides dielectrophoretic ejection force on the dispersed phase from the pores which will appreciably lengthen the service-life of the membrane.

Experimental

Two types of electrode assembly were designed. First electrode assembly is of needle-plate type. It consisted of a copper wire (1 cm length, 0.1 mm tip dia) placed perpendicularly at 5 cm apart from a copper plate (3 × 7 cm) serving as the second electrode. These two electrodes are permanently fixed in a suitable glass container (10 × 8 × 4 cm). In this assembly, non-uniform electric field is produced near the electrodes (a.c. 10–50 V, 50 Hz–120 kHz). In the second type of electrode system called slotted dielectrophoretic cell (10 × 8 × 4 cm), sharp nonhomogenous electric field is produced (a.c. 10–50 V, 50 Hz–120 kHz) between two planoparallel copper electrodes (3 × 5 cm) 2.5–5.8 cm apart and a special configuration perforated dielectric barrier made of teflon (3.5 × 5.0 cm, thickness 8 mm) having 0.5–4.0 mm slot size was placed between the electrodes. The configuration and size of perforation were varied according to the requirement of the experiment. The complete assembly of electrodes and dielectric barrier was fixed in a glass cell of suitable size. In this type of electrode system the non-homogeneity of electric field is produced sufficiently away from the electrode regions. Moreover, the strength of non-uniform electric field can be conveniently controlled by changing the distance of separation of electrodes, and size of the slots or perforations of the dielectric barrier.

In order to prepare the reconstituted milk whey, doubletoned milk was treated with a mixture of 0.1 M sodium acetate and 0.1 M acetic acid (1 : 100) till the whole casein part was precipitated. It was filtered and the whey so obtained containing the water-soluble proteins (i.e. lactalbumin and lactoglobulin) was concentrated on a water-bath till 20% reduction of volume. This was designated as suspension-A. Then curd from the pasturised milk was prepared and butter was extracted by cooling and churning the curd. The remaining butter milk suspension containing casein protein and non-casein protein (lactoglobulins + lactalbumins) along with other electrolytes intact, was homogenised. Butter obtained was defatted and butter serum obtained after the defatting was mixed with the butter milk. This was designated as suspension-B. Then suspension-B was added to suspension-A till the total suspended solid (TSS) of the resultant suspension reached upto 3.0%.

This reconstituted milk whey after homogenisation was taken in the dielectrophoretic cell for the purpose of study.

In the first phase, the experiments were conducted with needle-plate type electrode assembly. The TSS of the milk whey was first determined⁷. The milk whey (sp. cond. $5.7 \times 10^{-1} \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) was filled in the electrode assembly. Dielectrophoresis was then carried out by varying the voltage (10–50 V) across the electrodes and the frequency (50 Hz–200 kHz). After the experiments TSS of solution was again determined and dielectrophoretic yield of separation of lipid-protein complex was estimated. Experiments were conducted at different pH keeping the other parameters, viz. voltage and frequency, constant. In the second phase, the same experiments were performed with slotted electrode assembly.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Mr. Inderjeet Singh, R & D Engineer, Micrometecs Pvt. Ltd., Ghaziabad, for providing technical help in the fabrication of power supply.

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